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E-LEARNING CHALLENGES IN TEACHING CONTENT IN ENVIRONMENTAL ENGINEERING WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF COVID 19.

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Abstract

The global COVID-19 pandemic has led to the suspension of teaching in many countries. At the university level, the urgent transformation of classroom classes into an online format has been carried out in a way that can be described as generally acceptable, although the measures taken have been adapted with urgency and not with a well-considered, a priori plan to teach a subject with a completely online methodology. Carrying to massive online evaluation is something that universities had never faced from an institutional perspective. Therefore, the faculty and the student must work together to provide a response that integrates methodological and technological decisions, while at the same time ensuring equity, legal certainty, and transparency for all actors, both internal and external. This article aims to analyze the treatment given to the formation and development of learning done through the e-learning platform, or Learning Management System in several virtual learning spaces in the Environmental Engineering program of two Colombian universities with different characteristics. These platforms use methods that combine tutorial and in-person teaching/learning of content in order to facilitate this experience in current conditions (COVID 19 for the large number of teachers who share this problem at this exceptional moment around the world).

INTRODUCTION

The teaching and learning of the tutorial modality are attuned to that of the classroom modality, the latter of which is characterized by the physical presence of the students and the teacher in the classroom. This interactive context is essential for the teaching and oral learning of a foreign language and the development of communicative competence.

The COVID-19 pandemic has directly impacted the educational systems in every country in affecting students, households, ministries, secretariats, educational centers, educators, and administrators. The closing of schools as part of measures taken to contain the spread of the virus has more than 165 million students not attending schools, from preschools to higher education, in 25 countries in the region (UNESCO, 2020). 2

The economic and social costs of the pandemic are still unknown, but an economic crisis unprecedented in modern history is looming. It is estimated that widespread declines in GDP worldwide will affect developing countries the most. The IDB's Macroeconomic Report "Policies to Combat the Pandemic" estimates a drop in regional GDP to 5.5%. (Nuguer, V., & Powell, A, 2020). 4

While the economic and social costs of the pandemic are still unknown, an economic crisis never seen in modern history approaches. [SOURCE] estimates that falling GDP around the world will be felt most acutely in developing countries. The IDB's Report, "Policies to Combat the Pandemic," estimates that GDP in [Latin America and the Caribbean?] has declined 5.5% since the start of the pandemic. (Or "The IDB's Report, "Policies to Combat the Pandemic," estimates that GDP in [Latin America and the Caribbean?] will decline by 5.5% between 20xx and 20xx).

This situation may be further aggravated in educational systems that do not have effective mechanisms for distance education in line with household characteristics 7, which may further widen the gaps between students with greater or lesser access to them. LAC countries have launched Remote Education Emergency Initiatives 8 to provide short-term solutions and maintain some continuity in learning processes.

The solutions adopted have depended on the capacities and modalities of each country, as well as the content available to build an emergency model of distance education. For example, most ministries had digitized printed educational resources (e.g. textbooks, libraries, etc.), educational portals and online resources for students and teachers. Few countries had content platforms and learning management systems. It is key to understand, however, that these resources were designed for an education that would otherwise be delivered in person or semi-in person and not entirely remotely.

Most governments around the world have temporarily shut down educational institutions in an attempt to contain the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic. These nationwide closures affect about 70 percent of the world's student population.

UNESCO is supporting countries in their efforts to mitigate the immediate impact of school closures, particularly for the most vulnerable and disadvantaged communities, and to facilitate the continuity of education for all through remote learning.

Current pedagogy seeks to provide a foundation for how to reach students of the present generation most appropriately so that they master conceptual, procedural and attitudinal knowledge for their daily life and career. This includes a foreign language, in most cases English, for international communication, as an expression of culture, and a way to update or educate professionals in training in Colombia, technically or humanistically.

In the face of current challenges, some studies examine the blended model between in-person and e-learning, which offers a new frame of reference for an educational implementation that differs from the traditional one; however, the necessary standards of excellence have not yet been achieved and the best ways to incorporate in-person learning in English with the activities of the blended model have not been explained.

The professional finds more opportunities to access cutting-edge research knowledge in this area of engineering in English. Online LMS learning is currently offered, but that does not rule out blended methodology as a bet on the successful development of skills in this language. Hossein Moradimokhles & Gwo-Jen Hwang (2020): The effect of online vs. blended learning in developing English language skills by nursing student: an experimental study, *Interactive Learning Environments*, DOI: 10.1080/10494820.2020.1739079.

1 METHODOLOGY

This article was developed in a systematic review using databases and institutional repositories using searches with keywords such as “e-learning,” “COVID-19 and education,” and “virtual education”

Analysis of the data

To say that face-to-face education is better than digital is completely erroneous. The possibilities of digital education have been brought to the table by such important institutions as the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), the University of Chicago, and the Universidad San Ignacio de Loyola. Let us reflect. Who is better prepared to face a challenge like COVID-19: the one who has studied for several years in a digital environment, and who is very familiar with this environment, or someone who is facing it for the first time? There has been talk of the democratization of knowledge, which

exists and is real, but let us speak of the "commoditization" of knowledge. (Nuguer, V., & Powell, A. 2020). 5

Knowledge 2,000 years ago was reserved for a few in educational institutions, but today it is accessible to everyone. With this, knowledge has expanded, and has done so with a marginal cost that tends to zero. Therefore, more than democratization, it is a "commoditization" of knowledge. Therefore, the most important thing in this Fourth Industrial Revolution is that we understand what is happening. We live in a present where the old does not stop dying and the news does not stop appearing. We are immersed in this transitive property where we do not know, yet, if we are analog or if we are digital. The generations that follow will live in a different reality.

A World Bank study says that, in four or five years, 65% of today's young people will have jobs that do not yet exist. Therefore, universities must prepare students for the new jobs that will arise, to use technology that has not yet been invented and to solve problems about which we do not yet know. Moreover, we must focus on the development of soft skills and digital skills, skills that the labor market will require. And what are some of those skills? Problem-solving, critical thinking, creativity, personnel management, emotional intelligence.

The purpose or intention of the assessment distinguishes, primarily, between the assessment of learning, which is designed to aid in the learning process y providing feedback to students (Mcalpine, 2002), and the summative assessment, which ends a learning period with a final judgment on the overall student performance (Earl, 2013. When the student is more deeply involved in the process of formative evaluation, through self-monitoring and evaluation, or by his or her peers, it is called assessment as learning (Earl, 2013). Additionally, the diagnostic evaluation tries to predict the future performance of the student body. As shown in Figure 1, there is a strong relationship between the time dimension and the functional dimension of the assessment.

Figure 1. Schedule of diagnostic, formative assessment. Source: based on Stalljohann (2012, p. 11).

Depending on the length of the assessment, it may be a partial evaluation, which focuses on some components of a subject, or an overall evaluation, when it tries to cover all components of a student, course, program, center, etc. When the focus is on transparency, there is a range between formal and informal (Mcalpine, 2002). Formal assessment is easily recognized by the student body, as in the case of examinations or evaluable tasks. Informal evaluation accompanies other activities and is not as apparent, for example, participation in a discussion forum on the virtual campus. The subject of the assessment may be a product when it is based on the idea of the transfer of knowledge from the teaching profession to the student body, but when more emphasis is placed on competencies, the process is a more suitable subject for evaluation. However, assessing how a task has been carried out is always more complex than evaluating the outcome of a task.

According to the origin of the evaluators, we traditionally speak of internal evaluation and external evaluation. Internal evaluation is promoted and carried out from within, by the members of the teaching team themselves, while in an external evaluation, the evaluated and the evaluator belong to different bodies. This dimension may include open evaluation, which refers to the practice of obtaining and presenting credentials by demonstrating what has been learned. In this way, the process and procedures leading to the evaluation of these credentials are known, rather than maintaining and imposing a monopoly on the recognition of learning.

An example is to publish instructions, questions and headings for the evaluation of these, in such a way that any external agency wishing to evaluate students in a course (whom themselves want to be evaluated) could do so. In this situation, for a given course there is no single form of evaluation, but there can be as many forms of evaluation as there are students; the assessment of individual performance is independent, that is, it is separated from the course content and its instruction (Downes, 2012). From the perspective of the actors involved in the evaluation, a distinction is made between:

- Self-assessment: students evaluate their performance.
- Heteroevaluation: evaluators and the evaluated are not the same people
- Co-evaluation: certain people or groups mutually evaluate each other, that is, evaluators and the evaluated exchange their role alternately (Castillo Arredondo and Cabrerizo Diago, 2009). Coevaluation can also be applied to situations where students are allowed
- to assess themselves while allowing the teaching team to maintain the necessary control over final evaluations (Hall, 1995).
- Peer evaluation: the process through which students grade their peers (Falchikov, 1995).

Coevaluation can be used for summative purposes, while self-evaluation and peer evaluation tend to be used in a formative manner (Dochy, Segers and Sluijsmans, 1999). Finally, based on the normotype, there is a differentiation between normative evaluation and criteria evaluation. In a normative evaluation, the benchmark is the general level of a given normative group. It establishes

the comparison between the performance of each student and the average performance of his group. Criterial evaluation refers to a prior criterion (evaluation criterion), or a precise and concrete determination of the expected yields (Castillo Arredondo and Cabrerizo Diago, 2009; Popham, 1980).

E-proctoring systems in education

The development of online educational programs has evolved significantly based on pedagogical models and advances in learning technologies, but assessment or certification of learning remains one of its weakest points. In situations with few students and models focused on teacher-student interaction (Seoane-Pardo and García-Peñalvo, 2006; Seoane-Pardo and García-Peñalvo, 2008), continuous evaluation-based models are perfectly manageable and admissible. On the other hand, when the number of students grows, as is the case of the MOOC (Massive Open Online Courses) (García-Peñalvo, Fidalgo-Blanco and Sein-Echaluce, 2017, 2018), models based on continuous evaluation alone are no longer as feasible. then tends to extremes that lead to the development of personality assessment in specific physical locations (Shuey, 2002) or to the use of disruptive solutions based on open assessment (Downes, 2012), which are often not widely accepted in formal university training. Accordingly, there is an increase in demand for technological solutions that allow for online supervision of an evaluation (Fluck, 2019; Pathak, 2016), due as much to the limitation of having to resort to an in-person evaluation for an online education, as to studies that support the idea that unsupervised examinations have a higher potential risk of inappropriate ethical behavior or inflation (Carstairs and Myers, 2009; Prince, Fulton and Garsombke, 2009). However, few studies make an in-depth comparison of dishonest conduct in on-site testing and online testing as they are conducted (Chirumamilla, Sindre and Nguyen-Duc, 2020; Sindre and Vegendla, 2015).

Remote monitoring systems are called e-proctoring systems. The use of these remote monitoring systems is conceived as an attempt to equalize the incidence of academic dishonesty between online and personality assessment tests (Harmon and Lambrinos, 2008), to lend a higher degree of confidence for both teachers and external agencies that must accredit the quality of the diplomas that are not taught person, but either 100% online or blended. There is an awareness that, as with the supervision of on-site examinations, there is no perfect virtual monitoring method.

An important factor that differentiates between private and public institutions is the recruitment of students and their performance in the Saber Pro tests, The tests on the quality of undergraduate in Colombia, now called SABER PRO, have been suggested as standardized external evaluation instruments that are part of a set of processes undertaken by the National Government in an attempt to assess the quality of public education and do inspection and surveillance. Castro and Ruiz (2019) show in the first scenario the following: "..., students with higher synthetic Saber 11 indices continue their higher education at a university, compared to a technical institution... good high school students continue to be good superior education students." Concerning student recruitment, studies indicate/the data indicate/analysis indicates that private secondary and higher institutions attract more students than public entities, however, when analyzing quality (average, low and high Saber Pro

scores) the public institutions in superior education . (Castro, M., & Ruiz, J. 2019). Secondary and higher education in Colombia as observed Saber tests. *Praxis & Saber*, 10(24), 341-24.

These efforts by universities now include exceptional regulations covering the different methods of online assessment, entailing not a change in the rules governing the organization of teaching, but rather an adaptation to the online assessment. These assessments differ from the methods traditionally implemented in teaching guides, guides that will need to be modified to record, in a general way, the methodological changes and changes to the evaluation system.

For virtual/distance evaluation tests, these regulations should consider general or specific contingency procedures in the case of problems that may arise (virtual classroom crash, video conferencing system, individual connectivity problems, etc.) and performance guidelines in such cases (Cordon et al., 2020). 4.

It is essential to collect evidence from assessments carried out through systems that ensure compliance with legislation on data protection and digital rights of individuals. The durability and accessibility of evidence must be guaranteed during the review period and legal custody in order to be able to deal with possible complaints from students, audits by quality agencies or regulatory compliance (Cordón et al., 2020).

Online evaluation of the theoretical and practical aspects of the subjects

In general, when using oral examinations or written response examinations, whether synchronous or asynchronous, best practice is to avoid questions that require memorized answers or that can be looked up on the internet. They should be replaced by reflection questions, which assess students' understanding, discretion, or judgment or which require the application of some type of cognitive process, for example, causing them to do some work before submitting/providing an answer. The levels of self-identification of students for the different tests are summarized as:

- Basic level: Access to virtual platforms via ID and custom passwords is personal and non-transferable information that de facto identifies students. Improper and fraudulent use of these identification keys can have legal consequences.
- Average level: equivalent to an in-person evaluation. In a videoconference, they are asked to show the camera an identification card (code or other equivalent documents with the student's name, surname, identification number and photograph) before taking a test.
- High level: biometric identity checks are carried out. It requires prior registration of students, installation on their equipment of complementary tools, and authorization to use the webcams and/or contents of the work desk.

Online assessment scenarios for the different parts of a subject can be classified into two initial categories: synchronous and asynchronous tests. In online teaching models, it is advisable to give feedback to students on the positive aspects of the tasks they deliver and the areas with room for improvement, and to inform them of the elements on which they are being evaluated. In a continuous evaluation scenario, there is permanent student-teacher feedback.

Online Evaluation Tools

So far there has been talked of online assessment strategies; this section gathers some of the most common tools that can be used to develop evaluation systems in university institutional technological ecosystems (García-Peñalvo, 2018a). Although most of these tools can be found on the different eLearning or LMS (Learning Management Systems) platforms, Moodle will be used as a reference because of its widespread implementation in university systems worldwide (<https://stats.moodle.org/>).

Strategies to promote motivation in online teaching

The motivational role that teachers play in online teaching is crucial. The way in which teachers help to develop students' autonomy and competence occurs in two ways: directly through learning activities, and indirectly through the nature and organization of these same activities (instructional design).

A well-known model on motivation to learn (ARCS, Keller s, 2010) proposes four categories of analysis. These are the categories of attention, relevance, confidence, and satisfaction, which serve as guides for the development of teaching strategies. They consist of capturing the student's attention, establishing the relevance of the learning, increasing the student's confidence, and helping to generate feelings of satisfaction through intrinsic and extrinsic rewards.

Another important methodological framework, which helps to create motivational strategies for learning, is proposed by Ginsberg and Wlodkowski (2000). This framework consists of four principles: establishing inclusion, developing attitude, enhancing meaning and engendering competence. The use of these principles can lead to high motivation and quality for all students:

Creating inclusive environments refers to the creation of learning environments in which students and teachers feel mutual respect, through rules, procedures and structures that allow the creation of an aid community. The role of the teacher is essential to this goal, creating an environment of open communication, treating students equally, and helping all students to express their ideas and thoughts.

Engendering competence refers to helping the student to develop a sense of effectiveness before a required task and the feeling that they can achieve a skill/competence with mastery, and in this way, attach importance to their self-control in terms of effort and strategies used. Accordingly, students need sufficient information, guides (e.g. Study Guide), and timely feedback to create their judgments of their needs to complete the assigned task. A key to developing skills in distance learners is to provide them with self-evaluation opportunities with an appropriate level of feedback.

And concerning unrealized and difficult to virtualize practices?

As soon as the health situation and the conditions of social distancing permit, within the academic period defined for the current course, priority should be given to those practices that, not having been completed or replaced, are difficult to carry virtually due to time and cost issues, with special attention to those in their final academic year of a bachelor's or master's degree. In the worst-case scenario, except for the final year of the degree, teachers can find that the skills that could not be acquired due

to the situation can be practiced and assessed; specific instructional designs, at no economic cost to students and with the endorsement of departments, degree committees and teaching bodies.

There is evidence of the benefit of considering blended training. Students must overcome resistance due to their existing ties to and experience with the teacher's presence and advice. That said, a study on students' perception of this modality mentions that it is now easier to accept new technologies and faster to learn their implementation, but they indicate that not all areas are possible to implement completely virtually. Aguilar-Salinas, Wendolyn E., Fuentes-FuentesLara, Maximiliano de las, Justo-López, Araceli, & Rivera-Castellón, Ruth E. (2019). Students' Perception of the Blended Model of Teaching Basic Engineering Sciences. A University Case Study. *University Education*, 12(3), 15-26. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4067/S0718-50062019000300015>

COVID-19, in public and private, means "Stay at home; but don't keep what you usually do at home." It is a call to action, it is an opportunity to innovate, to adopt simulation methodologies and virtual laboratories that are necessary and now mandatory to consider in curricula.

2 RESULTS

Online distance education continues to grow in universities today, and at this time when almost every country in the world is affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, it is one of the alternatives for students to access educational programs from their homes. Accordingly, teachers must pay attention to motivation, understanding its complexity and multifaceted nature, to design and develop successful, quality learning experiences. They should also use teaching strategies that include aspects of motivation such as meaning and expectation, which help to understand complex theories, concepts and evidence.

The motivation for online learning involves stimulating, sustaining and giving direction to the student learning, in the context of teaching designed for this purpose that determines its expression as a permanent activity for self-improvement.

Achieving motivation in the online teaching and learning process requires the development of activities that enable a proactive attitude that is conscious of inquiry and the content search. In this way, learning will implicitly bring the integration of the students' intention to acquire knowledge and develop their intellect, to the extent to which they are taught to think, to express their ideas, to reflect, to argue and to value what they learn and can thus operate with knowledge towards new and higher levels of demand that stimulate their development.

3 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The COVID-19 pandemic has created an unprecedented situation in all areas of education. The state of lockdown has affected all levels of education. This article focuses on the specific case of university studies and more specifically on in-person universities that have had to make an emergency

adaptation of in-person classes to a remote format that, in the best cases, have been able to integrate some of the basic principles of quality online education.

What was initially proposed as a replacement for teaching activities has inevitably led to non-classroom assessment scenarios that have traditionally been seen as the most complex aspect of managing university degrees online, beyond continuous assessment activities, most universities, whether remote or online, base their assessment processes on formats that require the physical presence of those who choose to take these tests.

If online teaching was already a challenge, and in many cases a shock, for the university community, remote evaluation is the biggest obstacle to completing the academic year. In addition to people's natural resistance to change, universities also face the technical limitations of systems designed to give specific IT support to mostly in-person activities and reluctance and lack of strong support from certain key players in the political and academic management of this process.

With the aim of assisting the faculty director and the student body indirectly, this article has included a set of recommendations aimed at designing online evaluation mechanisms and strategies, leading to a fair evaluation process for all. They are exactly that, recommendations, never impositions or absolute truths, because academic freedom and decision-making belong to the faculty. Professors must take their students into account in all phases of the instructional design of teaching activities and evaluations, as well as inform them in detail of the decisions made and the changes that the subject will undergo due as a consequence of the sudden causes of this crisis. In the context of these sudden changes, many teaching adaptations have had to be made in urgent conditions, so as not to paralyze academic activity.

Furthermore, if no one is to be excluded or harmed by the conditions resulting from distance education, the possibilities and students' limitations and impacts must be known in order to establish contingency plans adapted to each case. The teacher should be aware of them and they should be integrated into the institutional strategy defined for this purpose. Finally, there is palpable fear and mistrust on the part of many of the teaching staff towards their students: they intend to exercise strict control over those being tested to detect all student practices contrary to academic ethics.

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